

HIVEMIND NEWSLETTER_02

Year one status update

Reflections from the Project Coordinator

HIVEMIND has now completed its first year of coordinated development. According to Project Coordinator Daniel García Guirao, this period has been crucial for establishing the foundations of a responsible multi-agent AI ecosystem. The consortium has worked across technical, organisational and conceptual layers to align architecture, requirements and early design principles. The first year has shown the value of interdisciplinary collaboration, with partners combining technical, human-centred and ethical perspectives to give form to the ecosystem that is now taking shape. These initial efforts have set a clear direction for the phase ahead, where the first operational agents will begin to emerge.

[Read more](#)

Current architectural view of the Hivemind framework

Scientific publications

by the UPC team

What About Emotions? Guiding Fine-Grained Emotion Extraction from Mobile App Reviews

This paper introduces a structured method for identifying emotions in app reviews using Plutchik’s taxonomy. It also examines how large language models can support the annotation process and where human interpretation remains essential.

Multi-Agent Debate Strategies to Enhance Requirements Engineering with Large Language Models

This study investigates how debate-based interactions among several AI agents can improve performance in Requirements Engineering tasks. It proposes a taxonomy for existing approaches and presents a preliminary framework tested on classification scenarios.

The two studies are available on the HIVEMIND website under Resources.

[Access the papers](#)

HIVEMIND explained

An animated introduction to the project's core idea

We have prepared a short animated video to offer a clear and accessible introduction to HIVEMIND. It presents the concept of humans and AI agents co-developing software within a coordinated multi-agent system and outlines how this approach supports development from concept to deployment. The video also shows where the system is being tested, including healthcare, disaster response and mobility.

[Watch the video](#)

HIVEMIND clustering work underway

Strengthening collaboration with aligned initiatives

HIVEMIND has started working on clustering activities with the aim of building a sisterhood of projects that share similar ideas and objectives. We have already begun holding bilateral meetings, and in January we plan to bring all projects together to start coordinating joint actions such as webinars, meetings, events and collaborative publications. The goal is to maximise impact, strengthen our community and foster knowledge exchange across initiatives.

Thank you for following our progress. We'll continue to keep you informed on the next steps and achievements as HIVEMIND moves forward. For more details, visit our [website](#).

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